

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LOTUS FIBER/ IBUPROFEN LOADED PVA NANO FIBROUS ADVANCED DRESSINGS FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF CHRONIC WOUND

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the development of an advanced wound healing dressing and drug delivery system using electro-spun nanofibers composed of Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) and Lotus silk. The addition of Ibuprofen as a therapeutic agent enhances the functionality of these nanofibers. Modern characterization techniques, including Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Fourier-transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), were employed to examine the nanofibers' morphology, chemical composition, and drug release profiles. The findings highlight the potential of these nanofibers for controlled and sustained drug delivery, offering promising prospects for innovative wound management solutions.

Keywords: Lotus Fiber, Chronic Wound Management, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier-transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Wound healing is a complex biological process involving a sequence of events that restore the structure and functionality of damaged tissues. Chronic wounds, including diabetic ulcers and pressure sores, present a substantial healthcare burden due to delayed healing and increased susceptibility to infections. Addressing this issue requires advanced wound dressing materials capable of accelerating wound healing, preventing infections, and ensuring optimal patient comfort. Traditional wound dressing materials like gauze dressings and even advanced alternatives possess inherent limitations, such as inadequate moisture control, necessitating frequent changes, and offering limited antimicrobial properties Gupta et al. (2017).

1.2. Problem Statement

Chronic skin wounds, notably diabetic ulcers, create complex problems affecting patient health, lifestyle, and healthcare providers. These challenges extend to life-threatening implications, particularly in underserved areas with limited medical access. Conventional wound dressings offer simplistic wound care, healing, and drug delivery methods.

1.3. Literature Review

Many studies have demonstrated that the use of electro-spun nanofibers successfully in the domain of wound management both in pre and post-operative conditions. Electro-spun nanofibers are relatively efficient in terms of their drug delivery capabilities due to the larger surface area they exhibit in contrast to other drug delivery systems i.e. bandages, hydrogels and other adhesives (Morais et al., 2023).

1.3.1. Properties and techniques used for extraction of lotus fiber

Lotus fiber, derived from *Nelumbo nucifera* (holy lotus), is increasingly recognized for its ecological and material benefits, notably in applications like wound healing. Traditional manual extraction of lotus fibers is labor-intensive and inefficient, prompting exploration into more advanced techniques. Methods such as microwave-assisted extraction and alkali treatment have shown promise in improving fiber quality. Microwave-assisted extraction, particularly with hydrogen peroxide, enhances moisture retention and whiteness but can reduce tensile strength with prolonged treatment (Zhang & Guo, 2014). Alkali treatment with sodium hydroxide increases fiber strength and purity, with effectiveness improving with higher temperatures and longer durations. Additionally, lotus silk, extracted from lotus seeds, exhibits desirable properties like biocompatibility and antimicrobial activity. Despite these advancements, challenges such as high non-cellulose content and extraction efficiency remain, underscoring the need for continued innovation in processing techniques (Johnson & Lee, 2019).

1.3.2. Smart wound dressing used for the management of chronic wounds

Despite the wide array of topical treatments, antimicrobials, and dressings available for wound care, there is limited data supporting the efficacy of many options. Clinicians often rely on familiar or anecdotal evidence, which can vary in effectiveness. Treatments range from simple hydrogel or saline to more specialized options like povidone-iodine, honey, and super-oxidized solutions, the latter showing promise in treating diabetic foot ulcers Chen et al. (2019). The choice of wound dressing can be daunting due to the numerous available options, from standard cotton gauze to advanced materials like foam, acrylics, alginates, and hydrocolloids. Silver-containing dressings are commonly used to manage bacterial load, but their long-term effectiveness is debated. Ultimately, while various dressings and topical treatments are essential, they cannot replace the need for proper debridement, offloading, and management of ischemia and infection (Li et al., 2018).

2. Materials and Methodology

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Polyvinyl Alcohol

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), identified by CAS no. 9002-89-5, was first synthesized by Hermann and Haehnel in 1924 through the hydrolysis of polyvinyl acetate with potassium hydroxide. Commercial production involves the continuous hydrolysis of polyvinyl acetate using sodium methylate or sodium hydroxide. PVA comes in two forms: partially hydrolyzed and fully hydrolyzed, with the former commonly used in food products. This odourless, tasteless granular powder appears translucent, white, or cream and serves as an effective moisture barrier in dietary supplements, foods with inclusions, and dry foods requiring protection from moisture. PVA does not occur naturally.

2.1.2. Deionized Water

Deionized water (DI water), also known as demineralized or DM water, is purified by removing most of its mineral ions, such as sodium, calcium, iron, and copper. This process eliminates charged particles (ions) but does not significantly remove uncharged organic molecules. Unlike deionized water, distilled water is produced by boiling and then condensing the vapor, which effectively removes both mineral and organic contaminants. Thus, while both DI and distilled water are purified, they differ in their methods and the types of impurities they eliminate.

2.1.3. Ethanol

Ethanol, a primary alcohol derived from ethane with a hydroxy group replacing one hydrogen atom, serves multiple roles including as an antiseptic, polar solvent, and disinfectant. It functions as a neurotoxin, central nervous system depressant, and teratogenic agent. Additionally, ethanol acts as an NMDA receptor antagonist and a protein kinase C agonist. It is a metabolite in humans, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Escherichia coli*, and mice. Classified as a primary alcohol, alkyl alcohol, and volatile organic compound, ethanol is also recognized as an ethoxide conjugate acid.

2.1.4. Lotus fibers

Lotus fibers are fibers obtained from various but typically from roots, stem and seeds of the aquatic plant *Nelumbo nucifera* which is found in tropical areas. Lotus fibers possess excellent

properties but not limited to; antimicrobial, anti-mycotic, anti-viral, hydrophobicity, biodegradability and non-toxicity.

2.1.5. Ibuprofen

Ibuprofen, a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) derived from propionic acid, was developed in 1960 as a safer alternative to aspirin. Its chemical formula is 2-(4-isobutylphenyl) propionic acid. Patented in 1961, ibuprofen was first used to treat rheumatoid arthritis in the UK in 1969 and in the US in 1974, becoming the first over-the-counter NSAID. It is administered as a racemic mixture, with the Alpha-Methyl-Acyl-

CoA racemase enzyme converting the R-enantiomer to the S-enantiomer in the body. The S-enantiomer is believed to be more pharmacologically active than the R-enantiomer.

2.2. Methodologies

2.2.1. Lotus fiber extraction using chemical retting process

Lotus fibers were extracted using the chemical retting process which is one of the preferred methods used by harvesters in Vietnam, China and India for textile purpose.

Table 1 Different types of retting processes and their features

Retting Type	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	Duration of Retting
<p>Dew Retting</p>	Plant stems are cut and distributed in the field exposed to the action of pectinolytic microorganisms that disrupt pectins surrounding the fiber.	Low cost and sustainable process.	Influenced by uncontrollable weather conditions and soil-contaminated fibers; reduces fiber strength, consistency and quality.	2-10 weeks.
<p>Water Retting</p>	Plant stems are submerged in water (river, ponds or tanks) where anaerobic bacteria develop and break down the pectins.	Produce uniform and high-quality fibers.	Large consumption and contamination of water (superior environment impact); extensive stench of fermentation gases and high labor costs.	7-14 days.
<p>Mechanical Retting</p>	The fibers are separated by mechanical means, such as a decorticator or hammer mill.	Simple process that produces huge quantities of fiber in a short retting time.	High cost and lower fiber quality.	2-3 days.

2.2.2. Preparation of Blended Solution

The polymeric solution was created via the magnetic stirring process, PVA of 12% w/v 16 ratio was dissolved in deionized water at 70 Degree Celsius for 5 hours, after that the 10%

w/v lotus fibers were added to the solution and lastly the drug ibuprofen was loaded at 10% w/v ratio for the specific application for diabetic ulcers and pressure ulcers.

Figure 1 : Blended Solution of PVA/LOTUS FIBER WITH IBUPROFEN

2.2.3. LOADED

Fabrication via Electrospinning

The blended solution was electro-spun at 14kv, TCD was set to 12 cm, and unfortunately, we weren't able to precisely control the flow rate due

to unavailability of the syringe pump at the research premises therefore gravitational drift method was employed at 270 degrees after trial and errors.

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Figure 2 Basic electrospinning setup

2.2.4. Characterization Techniques

We characterize materials using SEM, FTIR spectroscopy, and UV-VIS spectroscopy

- **SEM**

SEM was used to analyze microstructures and surface morphology. It operates by emitting an electron beam onto the sample, detecting secondary electrons to provide insights into the sample's topography and elemental composition (Geng, Tian & Zhang, 2019).

- **FTIR**

FTIR spectroscopy was employed to analyze molecular structures and functional groups within the samples. It measures the absorption of infrared light by the sample, providing valuable chemical information (Johnson & Lee, 2019).

- **Dialysis bag method**

The dialysis bag method was used to study drug release kinetics from the electro-spun fibers. It involves placing the drug-loaded fibers in a dialysis bag submerged in a buffer solution to simulate physiological conditions (Mosallanezhad et al., 2022).

• **UV-VIS spectroscopy**

UV-VIS spectroscopy was utilized for quantitative analysis of drug concentrations in solution. It measures the absorption of UV or visible light by the sample, correlating absorbance with analyte concentration (Hajjalyani et al., 2018).

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Fabricated scaffold/patch

Figure 3 depicts the fabricated patches integrated into medical adhesive tape and duct tape for application at infection sites

Figure 3 Fabricated patches are placed in medical adhesive tape and in duct

3.2. Morphology characterization using SEM

SEM analysis (Figure 4) revealed uniform, bead-free nanofibers with diameters ranging from 250 nm to 380 nm. This variance from typical

nanofiber diameters (150 nm to 300 nm) suggests morphological changes attributed to the presence of lotus silk and ibuprofen. ImageJ software enhanced the SEM images and facilitated fiber occurrence calculations.

Figure 4 SEM Of Fabricated Scaffold

3.3. Chemical composition analysis using FTIR

FTIR analysis (Figure 5) confirmed the presence of PVA and lotus silk in the electro-spun nanofibers. Characteristic peaks at 3280 cm⁻¹

(PVA hydroxyl group) and 1740 cm⁻¹ (lotus silk carbonyl group from lignin) validated their incorporation. Specific ibuprofen peaks, notably at 1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O group), confirmed successful encapsulation. Origin Pro software plotted the FTIR spectra and automatically identified functional groups.

Figure 5 Transmittance FTIR Of Electro-spun PVA/Lotus Fiber Loaded With Ibuprofen

3.4. Drug release studies

Drug release studies (Table 2 & Figure 6) demonstrated controlled release from the electro-spun nanofibers over time. The profile indicated sustained release typical of 1st-order pharmacokinetic systems, with approximately

18% release in the first 24 hours and a cumulative release of 90% over 7 days. This sustained release profile highlights the potential for prolonged topical drug delivery.

Table 2 Relationship between absorbances and drug release over 7 days of time and the pure pbs solution where no absorbance was noted

Time (hours)	Percentage of Ibuprofen Released	Absorbance
0	0.00	0.00
24	19.8	0.198
48	36.6	0.366
72	50.3	0.503
96	62.1	0.621
120	74.5	0.745
144	84.9	0.849
168	94.4	0.944

Figure 6 1st Order Drug release kinetics of PVA/Lotus fiber with 10% loaded ibuprofen at room temperature.

4. Conclusion

The successful fabrication of PVA/Lotus silk electro-spun nanofibers loaded with topical drugs represents a promising advancement for wound healing and drug delivery applications. The nanofibers exhibited uniform morphology, and FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of PVA, lotus silk, and ibuprofen. Controlled drug release profiles suggest potential benefits for sustained wound treatment. Integration of PVA and lotus silk offers a novel approach to develop wound dressings with antibacterial and water-resistant properties. Further studies and in vivo testing are necessary to fully explore their therapeutic potential.

4.1. Future Prospects

The developed wound patch can be further enhanced by incorporating various drugs tailored to specific applications across different pathologies. Implementation of colour-changing chemical agents could indicate wound healing stages. Future clinical trials are essential to validate efficacy and safety before commercialization, ensuring compliance with regulatory authorities such as DRAP and FDA.

4.2. Limitations

Prior to market launch, the fabricated patch requires rigorous in vivo testing to validate its efficacy in treating chronic wounds. Compliance with regulatory approvals from healthcare authorities, including DRAP and FDA, is mandatory for product acceptance and patient safety assurance.

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